

ISSN (p): 3030-3362

№ 6 (28)

27.06.2025

IF 2024
11.7

RTADQIQ VA TATBIQ

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

S C I E N C E S

Exact, Natural, Political, Social, Economic, Technical, Medical, Pedagogical

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

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Registered in the Agency of
Information and Mass
Communications under the
Administration of the
President of the Republic of
Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023
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Dasturlash asoslari fanidan online olimpiada platformasini yaratish texnologiyalari

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Annottasiya. Mazkur ishda yakuniy oline olimpiada shaffof o'tkazish muhimligini hisobga olgan holda. Talabalar dasturlash asoslari fanidan olimpiada jarayonida bu platformaga dastur kodlarini joylab yuboradi, platforma esa kodni to'g'ri yoki noto'g'riligini inson omilisiz tekshirib javob qaytaradi. Natijalar shu vaqtning o'zida talabaga ma'lum bo'ladi. Bu platformadan ko'zlangan maqsad talabalar bilimini shaffof aniqlashga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: mijoz - server, Veb-portal, Dasturiy ta'minot, axborot-kommunikasiya texnologiyasi

Технологии создания онлайн-олимпиадной платформы по основам программирования

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Аннотация. В данной работе итоговая онлайн-олимпиада проводится с учетом важности прозрачного проведения. В ходе олимпиады по основам программирования студенты отправляют на эту платформу программные коды, а платформа проверяет код на корректность или некорректность без участия человека и возвращает ответ. Результаты сразу же становятся известны студенту. Предполагаемая цель данной платформы — прозрачно определить знания студентов.

Ключевые слова: клиент-сервер, веб-портал, программное обеспечение, информационно-коммуникационные технологии

Technologies for creating an online Olympiad platform on the basics of programming

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Annotation. In this work, the final online Olympiad is held taking into account the importance of transparent conduct. During the Olympiad on the basics of programming, students submit program codes to this platform, and the platform checks the code for correctness or incorrectness without human intervention and returns a response. The results are immediately known to the student. The intended purpose of this platform is to transparently determine the knowledge of students.

Keywords: client - server, Web portal, Software, information and communication technology.

Hozirda axborot texnologiyalari bo'yicha olimpiadalar o'tkazish, dasturlash bo'yicha olimpiadalar ham katta talabga ega. Ular orasida eng mashhurlari.

Rossiyada dasturlash olimpiadalarini o'tkazishning eng mashhur markazlaridan biri bu Taganrog davlat universiteti bo'lib, u bajarilgan topshiriqlarni tekshirish uchun o'zining avtomatlashtirilgan tizimiga ega. Ushbu tizim yangi ishtirokchilar uchun ochiq va muntazam virtual musobaqalarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Hozirgi vaqtda Rossiyada dasturlash darajasi tez sur'atlar bilan o'sib bormoqda, shuning uchun dasturlash allaqachon maktabdan o'rganilmoqda va har yili axborot texnologiyalari va dasturlash bo'yicha maktab, shahar va boshqa olimpiadalar o'tkaziladi. Maqsad onlayn dasturlash olimpiadalarini o'tkazish uchun veb-portalni ishlab chiqish.

Ma'lumotlar bazasini yaratishda predmet sohasini tahlil qilish, mohiyat-alloqa (Entity-Relationship) modellarini tuzish va jadvallar o'rtasidagi bog'lanishlarni aniqlash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Jadvallar o'rtasidagi bog'lanishlar odatda quyidagi shakllarda bo'ladi:

- Birga-bir (1:1) aloqa
- Birga-ko'p (1:N) aloqa

Ko'pga-ko'p (M:N) aloqa

Birga-bir (1:1) aloqa ikki jadval orasida har bir yozuv faqat bitta tegishli yozuvga ega bo'lgan holatlarda qo'llaniladi. Bunday aloqalarni yaratishda har ikkala

jadvalda asosiy kalit (Primary Key) sifatida foydalaniladigan ustunlar orqali bog‘lanish amalga oshiriladi.

drawdb.app muhiti orqali bunday aloqalarni vizual tarzda yaratish mumkin. Diagrammada jadval ustunlari aniqlanadi va bog‘lovchi ustunlar (odatda id yoki tashqi kalit — foreign key) orqali jadvallar bog‘lanadi.

Misol:

Foydalanuvchi (User) va Profil (Profile) jadvallari orasidagi birga–bir bog‘lanishni ko‘rib chiqamiz. Har bir foydalanuvchi faqat bitta profilga ega, va har bir profil faqat bitta foydalanuvchiga tegishli

1-rasmda Birga-bir aloqaga misol keltirilgan va tartib raqamga tartib raqam bog‘lanadi.

Ma’lumotlar bazasi dizaynida **birga–ko‘p (1:N)** aloqa eng ko‘p uchraydigan aloqalardan biridir. Bu aloqa turida **asosiy jadvaldagi har bir yozuvga** kichik jadvaldan **bir nechta yozuvlar** to‘g‘ri keladi.

Aloqa mohiyati:

Siz yaratgan modelda:

- Har **bitta foydalanuvchi (User)** bir nechta **yechimlar (Solution)** yuborishi mumkin.
- Har bir **yechim** esa **faqat bitta foydalanuvchiga** tegishli bo‘ladi.
- Bu – **birga–ko‘p (1:N)** aloqaning aniq misolidir.

2-rasm. Birga-ko'p aloqaga misol

Ushbu birga-ko'p aloqaga misol keltirilgan va jadvallarning ma'lumotlari boshqa jadval ma'lumotlaridan bog'langan holda to'ldirish.

Ko'pga-ko'p aloqa. Ushbu ko'pga-ko'p aloqa turi ma'lumotlar bazasida o'zaro mustaqil jadval yozuvlari bir-biriga ko'plab marta bog'lanishi kerak bo'lgan holatlarda qo'llaniladi. Bunday bog'lanish strukturasi yaratish uchun oraliq jadval (bog'lovchi jadval)dan foydalaniladi. Jadvaldagi yozuvlar **ikki asosiy jadvaldagi takrorlanmaydigan ma'lumotlar orqali** o'zaro bir nechta marta bog'lanadi.

Dastur ishga tushgandan keyin asosiy oyna ko'rinishi, Bu yerda to'g'ri foydalanovchilar ro'yxatdan o'tishlari uchun maxsus "ro'yxatdan o'tish" tugmasi qo'yilgan.

3-rasm. Dasturiy vosita asosiy oynasining umumiy ko'rinishi.

Ish davomida dasturlash bo'yicha onlayn olimpiadalarni o'tkazish tizimi simulyatsiya qilindi.

Mavzu sohasini o'rganish IDEF0, DFD va UML metodologiyalaridan foydalangan holda kontseptual model asosida amalga oshirildi. CASE texnologiyalaridan foydalangan holda, bu kontseptual modelni loyihalash jarayonini soddalashtirishga imkon berdi.

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Jurnal haqida

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali Fer-Teach MChJ tomonidan tashkil etilgan. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023 yil 3 mayda №078777 raqam bilan ro‘yxatga olingan.

ISSN 3030-3362

Jurnalda texnologiya sohasidagi ixtisoslashtirilgan jurnal bo‘lib, texnik fanlarning turli sohalari: fizika, matematika, axborot texnologiyalari bo‘yicha tadqiqot va ishlanmalarning barcha asosiy yo‘nalishlarini qamrab oladi. Jurnalda tilshunoslik, o‘qitish metodikasi va texnika fanlarining rivojlanish tarixiga oid ilmiy maqolalar ham chop etiladi.

Manzil: 15010, Farg‘ona viloyati, Farg‘ona shahri, ko‘ch. Solima, 23/4, kvartira. 26

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Web-sayt: <https://rai-journal.uz/>

Tillar: o‘zbek, rus, ingliz, qoraqalpoq

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Научно-методический журнал «Исследования и внедрение» учрежден ООО «FerTeach». Данный журнал зарегистрирован номером № 078777 Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан от 3 мая 2023 года.

ISSN 3030-3362

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области технологий и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физика, математика, информационные технологии. Журнал также публикует научные статьи по языкознанию, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

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About the journal

The scientific and methodological journal "Research and Implementation" was founded by Fer-Teach LLC. This journal is registered under number 078777 by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 3, 2023.

ISSN 3030-3362

"Research and Implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all the main areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

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Website: <https://rai-journal.uz/>

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

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